

Pancreatic islets injury by electroporation

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Background: Microporation is a modification of electroporation technique, which can be used for introduction of macromolecules into pancreatic islet cells. Using short electric pulses, the micro pores within a cellular membrane are created. Nucleic acids can subsequently enter the cell. We tested, potential detrimental effects of microporation as a transfection method for siRNA introduction into pancreatic islet (PI) cells.

Methods: Male Brown Norway rats 10 – 12 weeks old were used as a donor of PI. PI were isolated by collagenase digestion according to a standard protocol. After overnight cultivation, microporation was used as transfection method (Neon, 2 pulses, 950 V, 30 ms). There were 3 samples: PI microporated with 200 nM siRNA, microporated without siRNA, and nontreated PI. After 24 h cultivation, islets were subjected to tests of viability and function – perfusion insulin release test, oxygen consumption rate, fluorescent test of membrane integrity (propidium iodide and acridine orange) to identify live and dead cells.

Results: All of the used methods didn't show significant differences among treated PI versus nontreated control. The insulin release during perfusion test and oxygen consumption rate (after stimulation by glucose in high concentration) were not impaired. Using fluorescent test of membrane integrity, the percentages of dead cell in PI were: 15,9 % after microporation with siRNA, 13,7% after microporation and 10,6 % in control PI.

Conclusions: Microporation with or without siRNA did not impair PI. Microporation appears to be a safe method for transfection of PI.

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